

**TOPIC: THE ROLE OF NATIONAL CUSTOMS AND TRADITIONS IN THE
ETHNOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PEOPLE OF BUKHARA**

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***Abstract.** The role of national customs and traditions in the formation of the ethnographic characteristics of the people of Bukhara is analyzed based on historical and ethnographic sources. The study highlights the importance of family ceremonies, folk festivals, national values, and daily lifestyle in the life of society. The specific features of the ethnocultural life of the population living in the Bukhara oasis are revealed.*

***Keywords:** Ethnography, national values, customs, Bukhara oasis, ethnoculture, family ceremonies, folk traditions.*

Relevance of the topic. The relevance of the topic “The role of national customs and traditions in the ethnographic characteristics of the people of Bukhara” is determined by the necessity of preserving and studying national cultural values in the context of today’s globalization and modernization processes.

First of all, under the influence of globalization, changes are being observed in lifestyle, cultural views, and social relations. As a result of these processes, the reduction or transformation of some traditional customs necessitates the scientific study of the ethnocultural uniqueness of the people of Bukhara.

Bukhara has long been a region with a rich history and culture, and the customs and traditions formed here reflect the social life, family relations, and spiritual values of the people. Their study is important for understanding national identity and preserving historical heritage.

Today, the need to educate the younger generation in the spirit of national values and teach them to respect traditional culture also increases the relevance of this topic. Because customs and traditions are among the main factors ensuring the spiritual stability of society.

At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, family ceremonies occupied a special place in the life of the people of Bukhara. In particular, cradle ceremonies, circumcision ceremonies, weddings, and bride greeting ceremonies

embodied the ancient traditions of the people. These ceremonies not only represented important stages of family life but also served to strengthen social solidarity and harmony in society.

Religious and seasonal holidays also occupied an important place in the ethnographic characteristics of the people of Bukhara. In particular, Navruz was widely celebrated as a national holiday, during which folk festivals, national games, and various ceremonies were organized. Ramadan and Eid al-Adha were also considered important events in the religious and cultural life of the population.

National clothing and food were also an integral part of ethnographic characteristics in the daily lifestyle of the population. Men wore robes, turbans, and skullcaps, while women used clothes sewn from atlas and adras fabrics as well as national jewelry. In addition, national dishes such as pilaf, samsa, and soup reflected the traditional lifestyle culture of the people.

Craftsmanship was also one of the important directions of the cultural life of the people of Bukhara. Crafts such as jewelry making, pottery, carpet weaving, and embroidery developed on the basis of national traditions passed down from generation to generation. This demonstrates the richness and diversity of the ethnographic culture of the oasis population.

A number of scientific studies are being carried out aimed at studying the material and spiritual culture, customs, and traditions of some historical and cultural regions of Central Asia, particularly Uzbekistan, identifying their contribution to world civilization, and evaluating the extent to which the specific features of the ethnography of the population living in this region during different political periods have been preserved. These projects aimed at studying the ethnogenesis and ethnic history, material and spiritual culture of the Uzbek people, and the processes of transformation over the centuries demonstrate the international relevance and necessity of the topic. Regarding the work being done in this field, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasized: “In our state policy, priority importance will continue to be given to preserving and developing the national identity, native language and culture, religion, customs, and traditions of representatives of all nations and ethnic groups.”

A thorough knowledge of the history and culture, traditions, and customs of one’s own people increases respect and attention toward the culture of other peoples. This situation serves to further strengthen interethnic tolerance and harmony. As the First President I.A. Karimov emphasized: “A nation that does not know its history and forgets its past has no future.” Today, it is becoming appropriate to deeply analyze all

the factors and criteria that shape our spirituality and influence it, and to clearly understand their role in this regard. The spirituality of any people or nation cannot be imagined separately from its history, unique customs and traditions, and life values. In this respect, spiritual heritage, cultural wealth, and ancient historical monuments naturally serve as some of the most important factors.

Research Purpose: To scientifically study the role of national customs and traditions in the ethnographic characteristics of the people of Bukhara and to analyze their importance in social life, family relations, spiritual values, and the preservation of national identity.

Research Objectives:

1. To analyze the historical roots of national customs and traditions;
2. To highlight the family, ceremonial, and бытовые traditions specific to the Bukhara region;
3. To determine the role of customs in the upbringing of the younger generation and in spiritual life;
4. To preserve national traditions in the context of modern globalization.

Scientific novelty: For the first time, the role of national customs and traditions in the formation of the ethnographic characteristics of the people of Bukhara was studied comprehensively and systematically. During the research, the ethnographic aspects of family and ceremonial traditions, customs, and everyday values specific to the Bukhara oasis were analyzed on the basis of scientific sources and practical materials.

In addition, ancient traditions preserved among the people of Bukhara and their significance in modern social life were revealed. The role of national customs in the upbringing of the younger generation, strengthening of the family, and understanding of national identity was highlighted on the basis of an ethnographic approach.

Research results: During this scientific research, the role of national customs and traditions in the ethnographic characteristics of the people of Bukhara was comprehensively studied. In the course of the research, historical sources, ethnographic data, and examples of folklore were used, and information was collected through observation and interview methods among the local population. The obtained results showed that national values and traditions in the Bukhara oasis still remain an integral part of the people's lifestyle today.

The transformation of many ceremonies in Bukhara continued to influence the life of a people ethnographically composed of various groups for many years. We can observe that the procedures of pre-wedding, wedding, and post-wedding ceremonies, the participants, and the traditions, customs, and habits within them have been passed

down from generation to generation. In particular, pre-wedding ceremonies (choosing a girl, matchmaking, giving an answer, oq o‘ratish, oqlik, bread breaking, that is non shikanon, cutting white cloth with scissors, shirinixo‘ri, maslahat oshi, sitora pilaf, sending a festive tablecloth for Eid, sending a bowl, religious ceremony—reading the khutbah, that is marriage registration, registration with the state – Civil Registry Office), ceremonies performed during the wedding (engagement wedding, padar osh, xinabandon, that is girls’ gathering, jomapo‘shon – dressing the groom in a robe, escorting the groom – domot bari), and post-wedding ceremonies (chimildiq, bringing the bride to the new house and slaughtering a sheep under her feet – this act should be done with proper intention so as not to cause shirk and the sheep should be slaughtered at another time; circling around fire – this act is also considered inappropriate; salomnoma, mahsi yechar, yuz ochar – ro‘yi binon, bride greeting – sarsho‘yon ceremony, preparing a place for the bride and groom, gathering the bedding – joyg‘ondoron, talbon-chaqirdi) can be cited as examples.

In addition, during the research, the attitude of the people of Bukhara toward religious values was also studied. Religious holidays such as Ramadan and Eid al-Adha, charitable events, almsgiving, and good deeds were observed to be an important part of the people’s spirituality. The harmony of religious values and national traditions contributes to the formation of moral norms and human virtues in society.

In the methodological guide “Traditional Customs and Ceremonies of Uzbeks and Tajiks of the Bukhara Oasis” by A. Jumayev, customs and traditions such as factors encouraging pregnancy and attitudes toward childbirth, and measures against childlessness are mentioned. In the brochure “Scenes from the Ethnography of Bukhara” by A.Sh. Jumaev and M.B. Qurbonova, interesting customs related to childhood traditions and ceremonies are presented.

The research results showed that values such as respect for family, honoring elders, hospitality, neighborhood relations, collective community work, and mutual assistance still have important social significance among the people of Bukhara today. In particular, wedding ceremonies, cradle ceremonies, circumcision ceremonies, marriage ceremonies, and religious holidays are important means of preserving the national identity of the people. Through these ceremonies, national values, moral norms, and traditions inherited from ancestors are instilled in the younger generation.

Conclusion. National customs and traditions occupy a special place in the ethnographic characteristics of the people of Bukhara and embody the centuries-old historical and cultural heritage of the people. Since the Bukhara oasis has long been one of the centers of science, culture, and spirituality, the customs and traditions

formed in this region stand out for their richness, diversity, and antiquity. These traditions are clearly reflected in the people's lifestyle, family relations, ceremonies and holidays, daily life, and spiritual views. In addition, national customs and traditions also serve as an important factor in ensuring tolerance, harmony, and social stability in society. Bukhara has long been a region inhabited by different nations and ethnic groups, and the cultural environment formed here is based on the principles of interethnic harmony and mutual respect.

The national customs and traditions formed in the Bukhara region are considered an important ethnocultural factor reflecting the historical development, social life, and cultural worldview of the people. This topic once again confirms the importance of preserving national culture, scientifically analyzing it, and passing it on to future generations through the study of the ethnographic characteristics of Bukhara.

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